

CONSTITUTION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN – GUARANTEE OF FREEDOM AND PROSPERITY OF SOCIETY LIFE

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Abstract: This article highlights the real goal of large-scale constitutional reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan, the issue of increasing the level of respect for human interests, well-being and prosperity in Uzbekistan.

Key words: constitution, new Uzbekistan, renaissance, reform, legislative initiative.

КОНСТИТУЦИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН – ГАРАНТИЯ СВОБОДЫ И ПРОЦВЕТЕНИЯ ЖИЗНИ ОБЩЕСТВА

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Аннотация: В данной статье освещается реальная цель широкомасштабных конституционных реформ, проводимых в Узбекистане, вопрос повышения уровня соблюдения интересов человека, благополучия и процветания в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: конституция, новый Узбекистан, ренессанс, реформа, законодательная инициатива.

INTRODUCTION

The Constitution is the basic legal document that is important in every country. According to academic experts, the constitution of a state is the face of the state because the social environment of that state can be understood depending on the constitution of the state. Поскольку Конституция является основным законом, на нее, безусловно, влияют события в жизни человека, ежедневный рост информационных технологий и глобальные изменения на международной арене. Мы хотим сказать, что конституция каждой страны нуждается в определенных изменениях, основанных на потребностях времени. Ведь, как указывал Шавкат Мирзиёев, «для обеспечения законности важно повышать

правовую культуру и воспитывать граждан в духе уважения к закону» [1]. Высокая правовая культура является основой демократического общества и выражением зрелости правовой системы.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An analysis of available sources indicates that the introduction of appropriate changes and additions to the Basic Law of the state is becoming a vital necessity. This process is especially important in the context of large-scale reforms carried out in our country in 2017-2022 and aimed at “increasing human dignity.” Despite the fact that the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on December 8, 1992, complies with international requirements, it cannot but require amendments.

Therefore, on July 15, 2022, Resolution No. 2304-1U of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On public discussion of the draft constitutional law on amendments and additions to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan” was adopted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Simply put, the rule of law means following the law. This principle underlies any developed country. The Great Amir Temur says that “I conducted the career of my kingdom on the basis of rules and regulations, so that no one could afford to interfere in its affairs,” showing that his state was governed by strict rules and laws [2.88].

The following main factors and reasons determined the need to begin constitutional reforms in our country: the first reason, it would not be an exaggeration to say that the need to change the principle of “state-society-person” to “person-society-state” was the fundamental basis for the beginning of these reforms; the second reason is to strengthen the constitutional and legal status of new social relations that arose as a result of reforms carried out in recent years of the development of our country. In recent years, under the leadership of the head of our state, large-scale work has been carried out on the digitalization of all industries. We must admit that it is impossible to imagine our present day without digital technologies. In particular, it is true that concepts such as digital economy, digital tourism, digital court, digital government services form the basis of our current development; the third reason is the need to strengthen the new mechanisms introduced in recent years to ensure the confidentiality of private property; the fourth reason is that life itself requires setting ambitious goals in the Constitution to preserve the ecology and purity of the natural environment and transfer it to future generations; the fifth reason is the improvement of the system of guarantees created by the state in order to ensure the rights and interests of young people based on the requirements of today.

In particular, it is important to determine the constitutional and legal status of the large-scale reforms carried out in New Uzbekistan in recent years in order to ensure the introduction of an education system that fully meets international standards, and society will grow into a wealthy generation in all respects.

In the new Uzbekistan, the creation of the necessary organizational and legal foundations to ensure freedom of speech, comprehensive development of the media, free activity and creativity of journalists and bloggers is literally the “fourth power” in the life of the state and society. strengthened his position and influence. We all witness these changes in our lives. Therefore, the diversity of opinions and development in society largely depends on freedom of speech and the free operation of the media.

This is the requirement of the time to organize the essence of the Constitution in schools in a completely new way, based on the age characteristics of students, using innovative forms of teaching.

In this sense, the head of our state must implement a scientifically based program to improve legal culture for each area and direction, all levels of education, and in this, first of all, seriously approach the study of the Constitution, and in this regard, curricula and textbooks on the need to create ideas.

CONCLUSION

The constitutional reforms being carried out today are of incomparable importance for the development of our people and state with the following positive aspects. Firstly, reforms, in the literal sense of the word, find their confirmation in life of the noble principle “for human dignity”. Secondly, ensuring gradual democratic reforms to fully determine the will of the people in managing state and public affairs is being updated. Thirdly, fair and just justice is established, the constitutional and legal status of modern socio-economic relations is determined. Fourthly, the position and authority of New Uzbekistan in the world community is noticeably increasing and serves to further improve the positive image of our beloved country.

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